

Field	Content
Title	Measurement of Discrimination in health care service provision: a scoping review protocol
Project	HealthIntelAct (grant agreement No 101168576)
Project number	Project 1.5
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Document Type	Zenodo Scoping review protocol registration (first public release)
Date	2026-01-22
Version	V0.1

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon Europe research and innovation programme under the Marie Skłodowska-Curie grant agreement No 101168576

Measurement of discrimination in health care services: scoping review protocol.

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Abstract

Background: Experiences of discrimination are linked to adverse outcomes across the life course, including poor perinatal outcomes, increased prevalence of maladaptive behaviours during childhood, higher rates of alcohol and substance use in adulthood, and a greater prevalence of schizophrenia in older age. Experience of discrimination within health care services is reported in 11% of respondents of the 2023 Special Eurobarometer on Discrimination in EU. However, scarce evidence exist on measurement and monitoring of discrimination within health care service delivery. Assessing and monitoring discrimination is essential for understanding its patterns, types, and the contexts in which it occurs, as well as informing the development of strategies at the macro, meso, and micro levels to address it.

Objective: The current scoping review aims to provide a comprehensive overview of available instruments for the measurement of different forms of discrimination (including: racism, xenophobia, heterosexism, sexism, gender binarism, ageism, discrimination on the basis of religion and cultural safety) within the health care service delivery context.

Eligibility criteria:

1) Concept: studies are deemed eligible if they report the development and validation of the instruments to measure discrimination, racism, heterosexism, gender binarism, religious discrimination, xenophobic discrimination, microaggression and cultural safety within health care services.

2) Context: health care service delivery i.e. studies reporting on primary care and specialist care are deemed eligible. Studies reporting on home based care and public health surveillance are excluded.

3) Participants: patients (inpatients and outpatients), family/informal caregivers, health workers and other health care service delivery interest holders are deemed eligible in the current review. Studies reporting on children (under the age of 18) are excluded.

Methods: Scoping review is conducted following Joanna Briggs Institute (JBI) updated guidelines and reported following Preferred Reporting Items for Systematic reviews and Meta-Analyses extension for Scoping Reviews (PRISMA-ScR) checklist. Search will be conducted on three databases MEDLINE all (via Ovid), PsycINFO(via Ovid). No restriction on the time period is placed.

Introduction

Discrimination, defined as differential and unfair treatment of a person based on their characteristics and beliefs, contributes to increase in avoidable health inequalities(1-3). These inequalities result from discriminatory systems which create “*unjust, unnecessary, and preventable differences in health status between social groups*”.(4)

Discrimination can occur at macro, meso and micro levels. At macro level occurs “*structural discrimination*” which reflects the societal systems, ideologies that perpetuate inequities and unfair distribution of resources resulting in health inequalities by influence on the social and economic determinants of health. For example, discrimination to access education, limits access to employment and leads to lower level of income which is associated with worst health outcomes. At the meso level “*institutional discrimination*” manifests, where discriminatory belief and practices are embedded in the functioning of the institution which result in intentional or unintentional, unfair treatment of certain groups. For example, discrimination in the health care institutions, can lead to underdiagnosis and undertreatment of marginalised groups. While at the micro level, occurs “*interpersonal discrimination*” which includes wide range of interactions between individuals that are discriminatory e.g. racist incident, name-calling, or microaggressions. The continuous experience of interpersonal discrimination is associated with worst health outcomes across the life course due to its negative impact at the behavioural, psychological and physiological level. (1, 3, 5, 6)

Experiences of discrimination (at macro, meso and micro levels) are linked to adverse health outcomes across the life course, including poor perinatal outcomes, increased prevalence of maladaptive behaviours during childhood, higher rates of alcohol and substance use in adulthood, and a greater prevalence of schizophrenia in older age. The intersectionality of discrimination, including structural, institutional, and interpersonal levels, alongside the overlap of various forms (e.g., race and religion), highlights systemic, multifactorial impact of discrimination on health and avoidable health-related inequalities.(1, 3, 5)

Despite the existing legal anti-discriminatory frameworks and programmes (7-10), the data from the 2023 special Eurobarometer on Discrimination in the EU shows that 21% of the respondents experienced discrimination in the past 12 months, an increase in 4% comparing to the results in 2019(11, 12). The experience of discrimination was most likely to occur among the people who consider themselves part of a minority group based on gender identity, sexual orientation, skin colour or ethnic group(12). When analysing the context in which the

discrimination took place, 11% of respondents reported experienced discrimination when using or requiring health care services(12).

Health care systems can contribute to reducing health inequalities “*if they enable access to services based on their needs rather than actual ability to access*” i.e. access to health care service should not be limited by the financial, geographical or other determinants of health (13). Given the health care system`s role in reducing avoidable inequalities and the trends in experience of discrimination in health care service delivery, measuring discrimination within the health care services is essential. However, there is scarce understanding how discrimination is being measured within health care services.

The need for a comprehensive framework to measure and monitor discrimination in health care services and systems is emphasised in the 2025 OECD report on Combatting Discrimination(2, 14). The existing reviews on this topic are focused on the impact of discrimination and report instruments used to measure one specific type of discrimination such as a systematic review conducted by Paradies et al(15) which reports on the impact of racism on mental health and instruments used to study racism as a social determinant of health. A review by Braddock et al(16) which extracted lists of self-reported instruments along with the psychometric properties which measure race and ethnic discrimination in children, not exclusively used within health care institutions. Similarly, a study by de la Torre-Pérez et al(17) focused on questionnaires used to measure gender discrimination, while Grey et al(18) conducted a systematic review on instruments that measure attitudes towards homosexual men and a review by Liu et al(19) reports psychometric properties of instruments used to measure ageism. However, these reviews are not dedicated to reporting instruments used exclusively within health care institutions and services. In addition, the existing published evidence synthesis report on one specific type of discrimination, not considering the intersectionality of discrimination.

Therefore, the current scoping review aims to map the existing measurement instruments used to assess different types of discrimination (i.e. the review will include concepts of discrimination based on race(1, 4), on sexual orientation(4), gender identity(4), age(20), religious beliefs, ethnic background and overlapping concept such as stigma(21) and microaggressions(22)), specifically within health care service delivery. Thus aiming to present a comprehensive list of existing instruments to measure the construct of discrimination in health care service provision and report on their psychometric validity.

More specifically, the review aims to answer the following research questions (RQ):

- **RQ1: What are the existing instruments used to measure discrimination in the health care service delivery?**
 - What are the existing, reported in indexed peer-review publications, instruments used to measure discrimination in health care service delivery?
 - What are the main characteristics of the instruments to measure discrimination in health care service delivery?
 - What are the psychometric validity of the instruments to measure discrimination in health care service delivery?

- **RQ2: What domains of discrimination are being measured in health care service delivery?**
 - What are the key domains of discrimination that are being measured in the health care service delivery (e.g. availability, acceptability, accessibility, quality of care, health-care workers discrimination, structural discrimination)?

- **RQ3: How do existing instruments measure discrimination in health care service delivery?**
 - (1) which actors provide the data, and (2) does the instrument capture discrimination as experienced by patients, enacted by providers, or embedded within organisational or systemic practices?

- **RQ4: Who are the intended users of the measurement of discrimination in health care service delivery?** i.e. the information collected by the measurement instruments on discrimination is used by whom within healthcare?

Keywords

Perceived Discrimination, Social Discrimination, Racism, Health Care Services, Measurement

Eligibility criteria

Concept

The current review is focused on two main concepts: “Concept I – Discrimination” and “Concept II – Measurement Instrument”. The eligibility criteria of both will be detailed in the following section.

Concept I – Discrimination

The current review is focused on studying “discrimination” which is defined by the European Commission Against Racism and Intolerance as:

“any differential treatment based on a ground such as “race”, colour, language, religion, nationality or national or ethnic origin, as well as descent, belief, sex, gender, gender identity, sexual orientation or other personal characteristics or status, which has no objective and reasonable justification”(23).

The review places no restriction on the type of discrimination being measured within the health care service delivery, including (but not restricted) to the following forms of discrimination:

- Racism
- Sexism
- Heterosexism
- Gender binarism
- Ageism
- Xenophobic discrimination
- Discrimination based on religious beliefs
- Cultural safety
- Microaggression
- Stigma

It is important to note that the concept of “stigma” will not explicitly searched for in the current review, instead overlapping concepts, terms, and synonyms will be used to ensure the inclusion of the concept within this review. Identified studies reporting on measurement instrument of stigma within health care service delivery will be deemed eligible.

Definition of each of the concepts considered eligible for the current review are reported in Table 1. From this point forward, to facilitate the communication the term “discrimination” will

be used in this protocol as an overarching umbrella term encompassing all the forms of discrimination listed above that are addressed in this study.

In the current review “discrimination” will be understood as a determinant of health, based on the conceptual model of the impact of discrimination on health presented by the 2022 *“The Lancet Series on racism, xenophobia, discrimination, and health”*. This conceptual model describes discrimination as being driven by two core principles: separation and hierarchical power. These principles operate across multiple institutions and social contexts, including education, employment, housing, and health systems. It shows how the interaction of separation and hierarchical power across these contexts accumulates, ultimately affecting individuals’ health. Importantly, the model also incorporates intersectionality, highlighting how overlapping social categories (such as race, gender, and class) interact across contexts to shape experiences of discrimination and health outcomes. Thus showing the complex, dynamic nature of discrimination. (1) (Figure 1)

Although the current review is restricted to the health care service delivery context, it will use the framework by Devakumar et al. 2022(1) to analyse each instrument according to the: 1) context in which discrimination is being measured, 2) level and 3) domain within health care service delivery. Further details on the data analysis are reported in the section on “Data analysis and presentation” of this protocol.

Figure 1- The Lancet, "Conceptual model describing how racism, xenophobia, and discrimination determine health"

Source: Devakumar D, Selvarajah S, Abubakar I, Kim S-S, McKee M, Sabharwal NS, et al. Racism, xenophobia, discrimination, and the determination of health. The Lancet. 2022;400:2097–108. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0140-6736\(22\)01972-9](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0140-6736(22)01972-9). | **Extracted from:** [Infographic - v02.1 - GRacE](#) (1)

Table 1- Concept I -Discrimination, eligibility criteria

Concept	Definition	Inclusion criteria	Exclusion criteria
Discrimination	Differential treatments or outcomes that are unfavourable towards a group or an individual according to some aspect of their actual or perceived identity, such as race, religion, nationality, physical ability, gender, sexual orientation, class, or social status. (1)	Studies that report on measuring instruments used to assess the experience of discrimination while receiving/within health care services ^a	Studies reporting on measurement instrument
Racism and Racial Discrimination	Unfavourable treatment or outcomes that a group or individual is subjected to because of their actual or perceived racial categorisation or identity. (...) operationalises racist ideology because this discrimination differentially allocates opportunities and resources based on hierarchical racial categorisations (1, 4)	Studies that report on measuring instruments used to assess the experience of racism and/or racial Discrimination while receiving/within health care services ^a	No information.
Sexism and Gender Discrimination	<p>Definition by Krieger, 2020 (4):</p> <p>Premise: Male supremacy is a natural fact. The status and roles of men and women (and boys and girls) naturally follow from differences in their biology due to being different biological sexes</p> <p>Privileged: Men and boys</p> <p>Target: Women and girls</p> <p>Beliefs: Misogyny</p> <p>Gender Discrimination components(17):</p> <p>Components:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Undervaluation: subtly treating a person’s abilities as less valuable because of their gender <ol style="list-style-type: none"> a) Different recognition: same work gets different merit or rewards (e.g. lower salary for same task) b) Different opportunities: unequal access to status or resources (e.g. jobs, promotions, scholarships) c) Different evaluation standards: biased criteria or assumptions about skills based on gender roles. d) Different expectations: gendered assumptions about interests, abilities, and appropriate behaviour (e.g. “women don’t understand engines,” “men shouldn’t show emotion”) 2. Different Treatment: clear, direct actions toward someone because of their gender. <ol style="list-style-type: none"> a) Different behaviour: less respect, social isolation, and lack of support. b) Verbal abuse/comments: Derogatory or offensive comments and jokes about a gender; Pressure to conform to traditional gender roles; Discouraging non-traditional gender activities, behaviours, or attitudes <p>Summary: unfair (discriminatory) treatment based on gender</p>	Studies that report on measuring instruments used to assess the experience of sexism while receiving/within health care services ^a	Studies that report on measuring instrument used to assess the experience of “sexual objectification” or “gender based violence”
Heterosexism and Homophobia	<p>Definition by Krieger, 2020 (4):</p> <p>Premise: Heterosexuality is the only natural sexual orientation Same-sex desire, behaviour, and identity are unnatural (and, by extension, deviant and immoral)</p>	Studies that report on measuring instruments used to assess the experience	No restriction.

	<p>Privileged: Heterosexuals Target: Persons who self-identify as or are categorized as lesbian, gay, bisexual, or queer (with terminology varying by societal context) Beliefs: Homophobia</p> <p>Summary: unfair (discriminatory) treatment based on sexual orientation</p>	of homophobia while receiving/within health care services ^a	
Gender Binarism and Transphobia	<p>Definition by Krieger, 2020 (4): Premise: Gender identity that conforms to biological sex at birth is the only natural gender identity Nonconforming gender identities are unnatural (and, by extension, deviant) Privileged: Cisgender persons who conform to their society's dominant gender norms Target: Persons who self-identify as or are categorized as transgender, gender fluid, or genderqueer, with terminology varying by societal context and language Beliefs: Transphobia Summary: unfair (discriminatory) treatment based on gender identity</p>	Studies that report on measuring instruments used to assess the experience of transphobia or discrimination based on gender identity while receiving/within health care services ^a	No restriction.
Religious Discrimination	<p>Religious discrimination is much like racial discrimination, but on the basis of religion and religious belief. Examples of religious discrimination include discrimination based on Islamophobic or antisemitic views. (1)</p>	Studies that report on measuring instruments used to assess the experience of discrimination based on religious beliefs e.g. Islamophobia or antisemitism while receiving/within health care services ^a	No restriction.
Xenophobic Discrimination	<p>Fear or hatred of, or discrimination against those who are considered to be foreigners. The targets of xenophobia are often groups or individuals perceived as outsiders to the nation and undeserving of the benefits associated with citizenship or national membership. (...)Xenophobic discrimination can be enacted through acts and measures that are explicitly motivated by hostility, but it can also be enacted structurally through policies and practices that are facially neutral.(1)</p>	Studies that report on measuring instruments used to assess the experience of discrimination based on persons nationality, citizenship or national membership while receiving/within health care services ^a	No restriction.
*Stigma	<p>An attribute or characteristic that is devalued in a particular social context, serving to reduce an individual "from a whole and usual person to a tainted, discounted one"(21, 24, 25)</p> <p>Components(21, 24, 25): 1. Stereotypes: negative belief about a group (e.g. dangerousness, incompetence, character weakness) 2. Prejudice: agreement with belief and/or negative emotional reaction (e.g. anger, fear) 3. Discrimination: behaviour response to prejudice (e.g. avoidance, withhold employment)</p>	Studies that report on measuring instruments used to assess the experience of discrimination which results from prejudice and stereotypes while receiving/within health care services ^a	No restriction.
Cultural Safety	<p>Cultural safety is about the experience of the patient. It is an outcome based on respectful engagement that recognizes and strives to address power imbalances inherent in the healthcare system. It results in an environment free of racism and discrimination, where people feel safe when receiving health care.(26)</p> <p>The concept of culture thus extends beyond ethnicity and includes, but is not restricted to: age or generation; gender; sexual orientation; occupation and socioeconomic status; ethnic origin or migrant experience; religious or spiritual belief; and disability. Cultural safety and competency therefore benefit all patients and communities. (27)</p>	Studies that report on measuring instruments used to assess the experience of discrimination of indigenous people and/or other minorities while receiving/within health care services ^a	No restriction.

Microaggressions	Brief and commonplace daily verbal, behavioural or environmental indignities, whether intentional or unintentional, that communicate hostile, derogatory, or negative racial slights and insults towards people of colour.(22)	Studies that report on measuring instruments used to assess the experience of microaggression of racial minorities while receiving/within health care services ^a	No restriction.
Ageism	“stereotypes, prejudice and discrimination directed towards others or oneself based on age”(20) Components(28): “1.three dimensions – stereotypes (thoughts), prejudice (feelings) and discrimination (actions or behaviour) 2. three levels of manifestation – institutional, interpersonal and self-directed 3. two forms of expression – explicit (conscious) and implicit (unconscious)”	Studies that report on measuring instruments used to assess the experience of ageism while receiving/within health care services ^a	

Table 1 caption:

^ahealth care services – an overarching umbrella term referring to context reported in Table 4;

*Stigma – explicit search terms for the concept “stigma” were not included in the search strategy, instead overlapping concepts, terms, and synonyms were used to ensure the inclusion of the concept within this review. However, articles reporting on measurement of stigma within health care service delivery will be deemed eligible.

Concept II – Measurement instrument

The current review is focused on identifying measurement instruments which assess discrimination in health care service delivery. Among the eligible instruments are different types of surveys (e.g. health surveys or population based surveys), questionnaires, tests or scales. (Table 2)

At least one of the aims of the study should be the development of an instrument intended to measure discrimination (in any form) in health care service delivery, or the evaluation of one or more psychometric properties of such an instrument. Studies that used an instrument measuring discrimination but did not intend to evaluate its psychometric properties, or in which the instrument was used solely as a comparator in the validation of another instrument, will be excluded.

The psychometric properties deemed eligible for the current review are defined according to COnsensus-based Standards for the selection of health Measurement INstruments (COSMIN)(29) and include: reliability (internal consistency, measurement error), validity (content validity, face validity, construct validity, structural validity, criterion validity) and responsiveness (Table 3). The instruments will not be excluded or evaluated based on their performance in these criteria, but rather whether they underwent any or multiple psychometric validations process. Thus ensuring that eligible instruments demonstrate a certain level of methodological quality.

Context

The review will focus on measurement instruments used within the health care service delivery context which includes: primary care, first level care, specialist care. The review will exclude measurement instruments used within the context of public health and home-based care.(Table 4)

Participants

This scoping review aims to study the experience of discrimination within health care service delivery. Therefore, the current review expects to include patients, family members, informal caregivers, and health workers defined as (Table 5):

- **Patients:** *“person who is receiving, has received, or has requested health services. It refers to all other terms for patient, including client, resident, person, and individual.”(30).*

- **Family/Informal caregivers:** *“Person(s) whom the patient wishes to be involved in their care, and act on their behalf or interests. Family is defined by the patient. This person speaks up on behalf of the patient with the patient’s input.”*(30)
- **Health workers:** are any professionals identified as health workforce according to the 2019 WHO international classification of health workforce(31), including:
 - Health professionals
 - Health associate professionals
 - Personal care workers in health services
 - Health management and support personnel
 - Health service providers not elsewhere classified

It is important to note that to ensure feasibility of the search strategy, current review will not explicitly included terms and concepts related to health care workers, as it is not possible to provide a comprehensive list of all the different types of health care workers. Instead, the search strategy will be focused on the health care service delivery context and any study reporting on the experience of health care workers will be deemed eligible.

Studies reporting on instruments used to measure discrimination perpetuated or experienced by children (i.e. patients under the age of 18) will be excluded as there is an existing systematic review conducted by Fukuda et al(32) with an inventory of more than one thousand measurements instruments of children’s ethnic and racial discrimination.

Types of Sources

The current review will include all qualitative, quantitative and mixed methods studies reporting on the development and validation of a measurement instruments for assessment of discrimination in the health care service delivery. No restriction on the time period or language will be placed. Studies which do not report full list of questions/items within the measuring instruments will be handled as following: 1) hand search for articles where the full items of the measurement instrument are reported and 2) contact the corresponding author with the request to provide a copy of the complete measurement instrument. Whenever full-text access is restricted, medical information specialist will be consulted to facilitate retrieval

Table 2- Concept II -Measurement Instrument, eligibility criteria

Instrument	Definition	Inclusion criteria	Exclusion criteria
Survey	A structured list of questions that collect data on a specific population (33)	Survey that reports questions on measurement of discrimination ^a within health care service delivery ^b	Survey which do not have a specific question on measurement of discrimination ^a within health care service delivery ^b
Health survey	Survey that is designed to gather information about health (physical and mental) and health-related factors. Health surveys generally include measures of risk factors, health behaviours, and non health determinants or correlates of health such as socioeconomic status. The range of measures that can be included is wide and varies by survey. Age, sex/gender and race/ethnicity are the basic demographic variables that are included in health surveys. Socioeconomic determinants of health include education, income, geographic region and rural/urban residence.(33)	Survey that reports questions on measurement of discrimination ^a within health care service delivery ^b	Survey which do not have a specific question on measurement of discrimination ^a within health care service delivery ^b
Population-based survey	Descriptive cross-sectional epidemiological study that is useful for calculating the prevalence of self-reported events or events measured during the investigation, generally employing a representative sample from the population of interest. (33)	Population-based survey that reports questions on measurement of discrimination ^a within health care service delivery ^b Examples: Second European Union Minorities and Discrimination Survey (EU-MIDIS II) Roma and Travellers Survey (2019) Special Eurobarometer 535 – Discrimination in the European Union	Population-based survey which do not have a specific question on measurement of discrimination ^a within health care service delivery ^b
Questionnaire	A group or sequence of questions designed to elicit information upon a subject, or sequence of subjects, from an informant.(34)	Questionnaire that reports questions on measurement of discrimination ^a within health care service delivery ^b	Questionnaire which do not have a specific question on measurement of discrimination ^a within health care service delivery ^b
Test	measurement instrument used to numerically asses knowledge or beliefs	Test that reports questions on measurement of discrimination ^a within health care service delivery ^b	Test which do not have a specific item on measurement of discrimination ^a within health care service delivery ^b
Scale	measurement instrument used to numerically asses abstract concept e.g. satisfaction	Scale that reports questions on measurement of discrimination ^a within health care service delivery ^b	Scale which do not have a specific item on measurement of discrimination ^a within health care service delivery ^b

Table 2 caption:

^adiscrimination – an overarching umbrella term referring to all the forms of discrimination listed in section “Concept I - Discrimination” and Table 1;

^bhealth care services – an overarching umbrella term referring to context reported in Table 4;

Table 3- COSMIN “Definitions of domains, measurement properties, and aspects of measurement properties.”

Domain	Term		Definition
	Measurement property	Aspect of a measurement property	
Reliability			The degree to which the measurement is free from measurement error
Reliability (extended definition)			The extent to which scores for patients who have not changed are the same for repeated measurement under several conditions: e.g. using different sets of items from the same health related-patient reported outcomes (HR-PRO) (internal consistency); over time (test-retest); by different persons on the same occasion (inter-rater); or by the same persons (i.e. raters or responders) on different occasions (intra-rater)
	Internal consistency		The degree of the interrelatedness among the items
	Reliability		The proportion of the total variance in the measurements which is due to ‘true’ differences between patients
	Measurement error		The systematic and random error of a patient’s score that is not attributed to true changes in the construct to be measured
Validity			The degree to which an HR-PRO instrument measures the construct(s) it purports to measure
	Content validity		The degree to which the content of an HR-PRO instrument is an adequate reflection of the construct to be measured
		Face validity	The degree to which (the items of) an HR-PRO instrument indeed looks as though they are an adequate reflection of the construct to be measured
	Construct validity		The degree to which the scores of an HR-PRO instrument are consistent with hypotheses (<i>for instance with regard to internal relationships, relationships to scores of other instruments, or differences between relevant groups</i>) based on the assumption that the HR-PRO instrument validly measures the construct to be measured
		Structural validity	The degree to which the scores of an HR-PRO instrument are an adequate reflection of the dimensionality of the construct to be measured
		Hypotheses testing	Idem construct validity
		Cross-cultural validity	The degree to which the performance of the items on a translated or culturally adapted HR-PRO instrument are an adequate reflection of the performance of the items of the original version of the HR-PRO instrument
	Criterion validity		The degree to which the scores of an HR-PRO instrument are an adequate reflection of a ‘gold standard’
Responsiveness			The ability of an HR-PRO instrument to detect change over time in the construct to be measured
	Responsiveness		Idem responsiveness
Interpretability*			The degree to which one can assign qualitative meaning - that is, clinical or commonly understood connotations – to an instrument’s quantitative scores or change in scores

Source: Mokkink LB, Prinsen CA, Bouter LM, Vet HC, Terwee CB. The COnsensus-based Standards for the selection of health Measurement INstruments (COSMIN) and how to select an outcome measurement instrument. *Braz J Phys Ther.* 2016 Jan 19;20(2):105-13. doi: 10.1590/bjpt-rbf.2014.0143. PMID: 26786084; PMCID: PMC4900032.

Table 4- "Context" eligibility criteria

Context	Definition	Inclusion criteria	Exclusion criteria
Health Care Service Delivery	<p>Health service: Any service (not limited to medical or clinical services) aimed at contributing to improved health or to the diagnosis, treatment and rehabilitation of individuals and populations. (35)</p> <p>Utilization (of health services): experience of people as to their receipt of health care services of different types. (35)</p>	Studies that report on measuring instruments used to assess the experience of discrimination ^a in health care service delivery	No restriction.
Primary Care	"first line health services" – such as health centres, general practitioner practices or clinics – as the primary level of care because they are close to the people they serve, accessible to all, and able to address a wide range of health problems.(36)	Studies that report on measuring instruments used to assess the experience of discrimination ^a in Primary care	No restriction.
First level of Care	"the entry point into the health care system, at the interface between services and community. Where the first level of care satisfies a number of quality criteria it is called primary care." (35)	Studies that report on measuring instruments used to assess the experience of discrimination ^a in First level care	No restriction.
Specialist care	"Specialist care is frequently distinguished into secondary and tertiary care. Secondary care is usually provided in local hospitals, whereas tertiary care comprises highly specialized care delivered in regional or national hospitals in order to concentrate expertise and complex, high-cost resources" (35)	Studies that report on measuring instruments used to assess the experience of discrimination ^a in specialist care i.e. at the local hospital level (i.e. secondary care) and the regional hospital care (i.e. tertiary care)	No restriction.
Public health	"a collective or societal approach aimed at "improving health, prolonging life and improving the quality of life among whole populations" (WHO, 1998). Public health covers the spectrum of health and wellbeing, from the eradication of particular diseases (World Health Organization Regional Office for Europe, 2020), to an increasing recognition of the political, commercial, economic, social and environmental determinants of health and social inequalities (Lomazzi, Jemkins & Borisch, 2016)." (35)	Studies reporting on measuring instruments used at national and international level e.g. Special Eurobarometer 535, Secon European Union Minorities and Discrimination Survey, Roma and Travellers Survey	Study reporting on measurement instruments in the scope of: 1) Disease prevention, 2) Emergency preparedness, 3) Social participation and 4) Communication with public

Table 4 caption:

^adiscrimination – an overarching umbrella term referring to all the forms of discrimination listed in section "Concept I - Discrimination" and Table 1;

Table 5- "Population" eligibility criteria

Population	Definition	Inclusion criteria	Exclusion criteria
Children (under the age of 18)	Patients under the age of 18	Not applicable.	Studies reporting on instruments used specific with children (under the age of 18).
Patients	Person who is receiving, has received, or has requested health services. It refers to all other terms for patient, including client, resident, person, and individual. (30)	Studies that report on measuring instruments used to assess the experience of discrimination ^a of patients while receiving/within health care services ^b	No information.
Inpatient	Patients formally admitted to the health care facility AND patients with overnight stay. (36)	Studies that report on measuring instruments used to assess the experience of discrimination ^a of patients while receiving/within health care services ^b	No information.
Day care	Patients formally admitted to the health care facility no overnight stay. (36)	Studies that report on measuring instruments used to assess the experience of discrimination ^a of patients while receiving/within health care services ^b .	No information.
Outpatient	Patients who are not formally admitted to health care facility. (36)	Studies that report on measuring instruments used to assess the experience of discrimination ^a of patients while receiving/within health care services ^b .	Patient receiving care at home i.e. Home-based care
Family/Informal caregivers	Person(s) whom the patient wishes to be involved in their care, and act on their behalf or interests. Family is defined by the patient. This person speaks up on behalf of the patient with the patient's input. (30)	Studies that report on measuring instruments used to assess the experience of discrimination ^a while accompanying of patients who are receiving/within health care services ^b i.e. discrimination can be towards the patient AND/OR family/informal caregiver	No information.
Health care worker^c	Any professionals identified as health workforce according to the 2019 WHO international classification of health workforce(37), including: a) Health professionals b) Health associate professionals c) Personal care workers in health services d) Health management and support personnel e) Health service providers not elsewhere classified	1) Studies that report on measuring instruments used to assess the experience of discrimination ^a by health care workers at their workplace. Discrimination ^a can be caused by the patients or health care institution, direct co-workers. 2) Studies that report on measuring instruments used to assess the perpetrated by health care workers at their workplace.	Health care service delivery beyond that defined in the "Context" section (and Table 4) of the current review.
Other health-related stakeholders^c	Any other actor within the health care service delivery which has not been explicitly defined in other criteria BUT that is related to health care service delivery e.g. governance structure, quality assurance mechanisms or other.	Studies that report on measuring instruments used to measure the experience of discrimination ^a by people within health care service delivery. No specific limitation on the population has been placed.	Health care service delivery beyond that defined in the "Context" section of the current review.

Table 5 caption:

^adiscrimination – an overarching umbrella term referring to all the forms of discrimination listed in section “Concept I - Discrimination” and Table 1;

^bhealth care services – an overarching umbrella term referring to context reported in Table 4;

Health care worker^c – explicit search terms for health care workers and/or other health-related stakeholders were not included in the search strategy, however, articles reporting on experience of

^adiscrimination related to health care workers were deemed eligible.

Methods

Scoping review will be conducted following Joanna Briggs Institute (JBI)(38) updated guidelines and Preferred Reporting Items for Systematic reviews and Meta-Analyses extension for Scoping Reviews (PRISMA-ScR) checklist(39).

Search strategy

A comprehensive multimodal search strategy is being developed composed of: 1) concept-based search(40), 2) key-word search and 3) inventory search, with the medical information specialist of Amsterdam UMC (JD).

The search strategy consist of the following steps:

1. Concept-based search:

- a. Sample search: the first author (AS) will search PubMed and additionally hand searched a sample of records reporting on measurement instruments deemed eligible for this review. Effort will be made to ensure representative sample search of the various forms of discrimination (as reported in section Concept I-Discrimination).

This sample will be analysed by the medical information specialist (JD) an discussed together with the authors AS and OBF regarding the definition, relevance and terms used to report concept, context and population.

In addition, “PubMed PubReMiner”(41) will be used to analyse the Medical Subject Headings (MeSH) terms frequently used in the sample search records. These MeSH terms will be analysed and relevant terms retrieved, excluding terms which may cause unnecessary burden of irrelevant records in the data extraction.

An iterative process will be employed where each concept will be discussed within the research team and chosen based on the definition, relevance for the review.

- b. Instrument inventory: the names of the instruments deemed eligible will be extracted from the sample search and incorporated into the search query to identify 1) all the studies reporting on the psychometric quality assessment of each instrument (later used for data analysis) and 2) identify other eligible studies to be included in the current review.

2. Key-word search:

- a. Key-word extraction from relevant evidence synthesis: the first author (AS) will run a simplified key-word search on PubMed, Web of Science and Scopus to identify and retrieve eligible evidence synthesis reporting on measurement of various forms of discrimination. The search strategies of each eligible evidence synthesis will be consulted and relevant key-words (including MeSH terms and free-text) will be extracted, forming a pool of possible key-words to be integrate in the final search strategy.

3. **Full search query**: The finalized search query will initially developed for the MEDLINE all (via Ovid) and later will be translated into PsycINFO (via Ovid) and Web of Science databases syntax. The complete search query will be reported in the final manuscript.

The medical information specialist (JD) will lead the search process, including strategy development, database selection, query adaptation, record retrieval, deduplication, and reporting in the protocol and final manuscript to ensure transparency and replicability of the search strategy.

Study selection

- **Title/abstract screening**: “Title” and “Abstract” screening will be conducted in open source AI assisted screening platform called “Rayyan”(42) based on the established eligibility criteria. Initially an inter-reviewer concordance will be done with a sample of n=10 records, the screening results will be compared and discussed to ensure the understanding of the eligibility criteria by all the researchers involved in the screening process. After calibration exercise, two reviewers will screen independently each record. Disagreements will be resolved by discussion and through consultation with a third reviewer.
- **Full-text screening**: reports for records deemed eligible in the “Title” and “Abstract” screening will be retrieved and imported into Zotero(43) for citation and document management. Medical information specialist and corresponding author will be contacted in case of difficulties in accessing full text report. Two reviewers will screen independently each report. Disagreements will be resolved by discussion and through consultation with a third reviewer.
- **Documentation & reporting**: to ensure transparency and reproducibility supplementary material will contain full search strategy applied at each database,

reasons for exclusion of reports at full-text stage. Screening process will be reported using PRISMA(44) flow diagram.

Data Extraction

The data extraction process will be conducted using previously developed and pilot tested data charting form. Microsoft Office spreadsheet will be used to extract following data from each of the eligible studies:

- **Study characteristics:** Year of publication, Author, DOI
- **Measurement instrument characteristics:** Instrument name, Instrument reported in Adapted or Original form, Instrument availability i.e. full availability of complete instrument (all items), Source of full instrument, Instrument type, Intended respondent
- **COSMIN properties:** Reliability (internal consistency, measurement error), Validity(content validity, face validity, structural validity, hypothesis testing, cross-cultural validity, criterion validity), Responsiveness
- **Discrimination type:** Non-specific discrimination, Racism, Sexism, Heterosexism, Gender Binarism, Xenophobia, Stigma, Cultural safety, Ageism, Microaggression, Other Discrimination, Other – Specify
- **Context and level (general):**
 - o Context in which discrimination is being measured i.e. instrument may have items measuring the experience of discrimination in the context beyond that of health care service delivery (e.g. housing, education or employment), which is indicative of the intersectionality of the measurement instrument.
 - o Level at which discrimination is being measured
 - Macro – Structural determination: law and governance
 - Meso – Institutions and systems: health care service delivery, housing, education, employment, legislation
 - Micro – communities and individual
- **Access to health care service delivery:** data extraction instrument on the access to health care service delivery will be developed using the combination of the framework by Devakumar et al(3) and Levesque(45) conceptual framework for healthcare access.

The data extraction from all the eligible articles will be conducted by two independent researchers, the data will be compared and consensus reached on the final data extraction.

Appendix I present an outline of the data charting form. Any modification to the data charting form or process will be reported in the final manuscript of the scoping review.

Data Analysis and Presentation

The search and screening process will be summarized in a PRISMA flow diagram, study characteristics will be reported in tabular format reporting frequencies of above-mentioned characteristics. Full list of eligible instruments will be presented in tabular format with name, instrument type, and source. The trends in the type of instruments available to measure discrimination and the context at which discrimination is being measured will be reported using heatmap.

Ethical approval

Ethics approval was not required as all data used in the study will be obtained from previously published articles and existing literature. No primary data collection involving human participants or animals was conducted, and all sources of data are publicly accessible

Funding

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2023 research and innovation programme under the Marie Skłodowska-Curie grant agreement No 101168576.

Conflicts of interest

None .

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Appendices

Appendix I: Overview of the data extraction variables

- Study characteristics
- Measurement instrument characteristics
- Measurement instrument quality [COSMIN]
- Discrimination type
- Context variables

Study characteristics

Code	Variable name	Format	Explanation
id	Study ID	Text	Unique identifier assigned to each record in the dataset
title	Study Title	Text (open)	Full title of the included study
yyyy	Publication Year	Numeric (YYYY)	Year the study was published
author	First Author	Text	Name of the first listed author

Measurement instrument characteristics

Code	Variable name	Format	Explanation
instr_name	Instrument Name	Text	Name of the instrument being evaluated.
inst_adapt	Instrument reported in Adapted or Original form	Nominal categorical	Instruments reported can be modified by the authors of the study, e.g. modified Krieger et al 1900 questionnaire, where instead of "gender discrimination" the author modified the question to the term "racial discrimination". Instruments that are reported in their "original form" i.e. Exact form and construction of items as the author who initially developed the instrument.
inst_full_available	Instrument availability i.e. Full availability of complete instrument (all items)	Nominal categorical	Full availability of complete instrument (all items). Is the complete instrument (full list of items/questions) reported in the study OR is there a reference to a study where complete instrument is reported ?
inst_full_available_source	Source of full instrument	Text	Provide the exact source where the complete version of the measurement instrument can be accessed. This variable specifies whether the instrument is found in: a) the study itself, b) an appendix, c) supplementary files, d) or an external study, dataset, or URL.
instr_type_main	Instrument Type	Nominal categorical	General classification of the instrument
instr_type_other	Instrument Type (Specify)	Text	Additional detail if "Other" selected above
resp_type	Intended Respondent	Nominal categorical	Primary target group responding to the instrument
resp_other	Intended Respondent – Other	Text	For respondent types not captured by dropdown categories
user_type	Intended user	Text	Primary target group applying/using the instrument to assess a form of discrimination

Measurement instrument quality [COSMIN]

Code	Variable name	Format	Explanation
cosmin_reliability_intenal consistency	Internal consistency	Binary (0/1)	The degree of the interrelatedness among the items
cosmin_reliability_measurement error	Measurement error	Binary (0/1)	The systematic and random error of a patient's score that is not attributed to true changes in the construct to be measured
cosmin_validity_content	Content validity	Binary (0/1)	The degree to which the content of an instrument is an adequate reflection of the construct to be measured
cosmin_validity_face	Face validity	Binary (0/1)	The degree to which (the items of) an instrument indeed looks as though they are an adequate reflection of the construct to be measured
cosmin_validity_construct	Construct validity	Binary (0/1)	The degree to which the scores of an instrument are consistent with hypotheses (for instance with regard to internal relationships, relationships to scores of other instruments, or differences between relevant groups) based on the assumption that the instrument validly measures the construct to be measured
cosmin_validity_structural	Structural validity	Binary (0/1)	The degree to which the scores of an instrument are an adequate reflection of the dimensionality of the construct to be measured
cosmin_validity_hypotheses testing	Hypothesis testing	Binary (0/1)	Idem construct validity
cosmin_validity_cross cultural	Cross cultural validity	Binary (0/1)	The degree to which the performance of the items on a translated or culturally adapted instrument are an adequate reflection of the performance of the items of the original version of the instrument
cosmin_validity_criterion	Criterion validity	Binary (0/1)	The degree to which the scores of an instrument are an adequate reflection of a "gold standard"

Discrimination type

Code	Variable name	Format	Explanation
disc_non_specific	Non-specific discrimination	Binary (0/1)	Mentions discrimination broadly without specifying type(s). Discrimination is defined as: " <i>any distinction, exclusion, restriction or other differential treatment of a person because of their characteristics or beliefs</i> "
disc_racism	Racism and Racial Discrimination	Binary (0/1)	Discrimination based on race/ethnicity-based Detailed definitions in Kriger et al 2020
disc_sexism	Sexism and Gender Discrimination	Binary (0/1)	Gender-based discrimination targeting women or perceived gender roles. Detailed definitions in Kriger et al 2020
disc_heterosexism	Heterosexism and Homophobia	Binary (0/1)	Discrimination based on sexual orientation. Detailed definitions in Kriger et al 2020
disc_gender_binarism	Gender Binarism and Transphobia	Binary (0/1)	Discrimination enforcing binary gender norms. Detailed definitions in Kriger et al 2020
disc_xenophobic	Xenophobic discrimination	Binary (0/1)	Discrimination based on being perceived as a foreigner (e.g. nationality, citizenship)
disc_stigma	Stigma	Binary (0/1)	The experience of discrimination which results from prejudice and stereotypes
disc_cultural_safety	Cultural safety	Binary (0/1)	Discrimination towards indigenous people
disc_ageism	Ageism	Binary (0/1)	Discrimination based on age.
disc_microaggression	Microaggression	Binary (0/1)	Discrimination expressed in daily verbal, behavioural or environmental indignities (originated from the racism)
disc_other	Other Discrimination	Binary (0/1)	Any form not listed above
disc_other_specify	Other – Specify	Text	Description of the “other” category

Context variables

Code	Variable name	Format	Explanation
Macro_Structural discrimination			
ctx_struct_law_gov	Laws & structures of governance	Binary (0/1)	Addresses policy frameworks, administrative systems, legal architecture.
ctx_struct_colonialism	Colonisation & racial capitalism	Binary (0/1)	Includes historical or ongoing colonial/racial power structures shaping inequity.
ctx_struct_politics	Political dynamics & exclusionary populism	Binary (0/1)	Mentions political climate, populism, or exclusionary policy shifts.
Meso_Institutions and systems			
ctx_inst_healthcare	Healthcare institutions	Binary (0/1)	Focus on healthcare organisations, policies, systems.
ctx_inst_housing	Housing institutions	Binary (0/1)	Explores housing access, segregation, housing policy.
ctx_inst_education	Education institutions	Binary (0/1)	Schooling, universities, training systems.
ctx_inst_employment	Labor market and employment	Binary (0/1)	Explores labor market, job access AND/or working environment
ctx_inst_legislation	Legislation & carceral systems	Binary (0/1)	Policing, prisons, legal enforcement structures
Meso_Spatial Determination			
ctx_spatial_segregation	Spatial segregation	Binary (0/1)	Physical separation of groups by race/class.
ctx_spatial_green_space	Access to green spaces	Binary (0/1)	Availability and access to parks, public recreational areas.
ctx_spatial_air_quality	Air quality & environmental exposure	Binary (0/1)	Environmental hazards, pollution, toxic exposure.
ctx_spatial_food_access	Access to fresh food	Binary (0/1)	Food deserts, cost/availability of healthy food.
Micro_Communities and Individual			
ctx_micro_communities	Community-level context	Binary (0/1)	Community safety, norms, cohesion, social capital.
ctx_micro_individuals	Individual-level context	Binary (0/1)	Personal behaviours, attitudes, psychological factors.